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Tayanch so'zlar: jismoniy tarbiya, sport, sog'lom avlod, chempion, futbol, kurash, sambo, og'ir atletika, suzish.

Rezyume: Ushbu maqolada mustaqillik yillarida jismoniy tarbiya va sport sohasini rivojlantirish uchun yetarlicha shart-sharoitlar yaratilganligi, jumladan, Qashqadaryo viloyatida ham sport sohasining futbol, kurash, sambo, karate-do, og'ir atletika, suzish turlari bo'yicha salmoqli natijalarga erishilganligi, sport ustalaridan Ro'ziqul Berdiyev, Botir Qorayev, Zafar Xolmurodov, Bahrom Avazov, Mavlonberdi Axmanov, Normamat Yo'ldoshev, Alisher Muxtorov, Sofiya Kaspo'latova, Tursunoy Jabborova, Shohsanam Toshpo'latova, Fotima Amilovalarning soha rivojidadagi o'rni va hayot yo'llari bayon etilgan.

Ключевые слова: физическая культура, спорт, здоровое поколение, чемпион, футбол, борьба, самбо, тяжёлая атлетика, плавание.

Резюме: В данной статье в годы независимости созданы достаточные условия для развития физической культуры и спорта, в том числе и то, что в Кашкадарьинской области достигнуты значительные результаты в спорте по футболу, борьбе, самбо, каратэ-до, тяжёлая атлетике, плавание, заявляли о роли и жизненном пути Розикюла Бердыева, Ботира Караева, Зафара Холмуродова, Бахрома Авазова, Мавлонберди Ахманова, Нормамата Ёлдашева, Алишера Мухторова, Софьи Касполатовой, Турсунной Джабборовой, Шохсанам Тошполатовой, Фатимы Амиловой.

Keywords: physical education, sports, healthy generation, champion, football, wrestling, sambo, weightlifting, swimming.

Summary: In this article, in the years of independence, sufficient conditions were created for the development of physical education and sports, including the fact that in Kashkadarya region, significant results were achieved in sports in football, wrestling, sambo, karate-do, weightlifting and swimming. Role and life paths of Rozikul Berdiyev, Botir Karayev, Zafar Kholmurodov, Bahrom Avazov, Mavlonberdi Akhmanov, Normamat Yoldashev, Alisher Mukhtorov, Sofia Kaspolatova, Tursunoy Jabborova, Shohsanam Toshpolatova, Fatima Amilova stated.

After gaining independence, Uzbekistan began to find its place in the field of physical education and sports. Realizing the importance of physical education and sports in ensuring public health, the government of our country started reforms in this field from the first years of independence.

There is not enough to say about the further development of physical education and sports in Kashkadarya, the transformation of sports into a mass movement, the restoration and modernization of national and traditional sports, the achievements of our athletes at the Olympic Games and international sports competitions.

If we talk about football, which is a game of millions, a number of world-famous players have come from Kashkadarya region. One of them, Rozikul Berdiyev, was born on October 22, 1971 in Kitab district. He played in "Yangier" club in 1992-1996, and in "Nasaf" football team in

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1997-2008. He started coaching in 2008 and worked as an assistant head coach of "Nasaf" until 2011. After the resignation of Anatoly Demyanenko in January 2012, he became the head coach of the football team "Nasaf" and worked in this position until May of this year. After that, he managed the youth team of this club. In November 2012, he was again appointed as the head coach of "Nasaf" and has been cooperating with "Nasaf" club to this day.

Botir Karaev, another player who made a great contribution to Kashkadarya football, was born on April 8, 1980 in Koson district. Famous football coach A. He learned football skills under Yumangulov. Later, he started to play in "Mash'al-2" team. Since 1997, he has been playing in the defensive line in the Nasaf club of Karshi and has become one of the club's main midfielders.

One of the real scorers who introduced Kashkadarya football to the world is Zafar Kholmurodov. He was born on October 15, 1976 in Shahrisabz district. In 1996, Zafar, who was admitted to Shahrisabz's "Hisor" team, started participating in games in "Nasaf" a year later. Being one of the most skilled strikers of our province, he manages to score more than 100 goals in official matches. [1-1]

There will be many people who will come and go for sports. However, there are few people who live and work with him for a lifetime. Bahrom Beknazarovich Avazov was born on January 3, 1970 in the village of Siiraq, Guzor district. Absolute winner of international competitions dedicated to the memory of Amir Temur and Pahlavon Mahmud. In 1998, he was awarded the title of international master of sports. In 2003, he was awarded the title of "Pride of Uzbekistan". Between 1991 and 2001, Bahrom Avazov was the champion of Uzbekistan in the 81 kg, 90 kg and absolute weight categories of wrestling. In 2001, he was found unmatched in the Asian Championship held in Tashkent. In 2000 in Antalya and in 2001 in Budapest, he won the first place and presented gold medals for our country. In the absolute weight category, he was also recognized as the winner of the 1996 Shahrisabz, 1998 international competitions in Khiva, and the 1998 Alpomish games in Termiz. Our athlete, who graduated from Karshi Pedagogical Institute (now Karshi DU) in 1991, worked as a senior teacher in this institute in 1991-2003. Since 2003, he has worked as the director of the Kashkadarya regional branch of the Children's Sports Development Fund of Uzbekistan.

From the first years of independence, Mavlonberdi Akhmanov was appointed as the executive director of the Kashkadarya Region National Wrestling Federation. In 1992, in the city of Shahrisabz, Kashkadarya region, he contributed to the organization of the "Amir Temur" international tournament, which was held for the first time in national wrestling, and mentored the wrestlers of Kashkadarya. In the tournament, one of the wrestlers from Kashkadarya, Abdugadir Pirmatov, was the absolute winner of the tournament, and Tura Avliyokulov won the first place in their weight category and won the presidential prize. In August 1992, Mavlonberdi Akhmanov was awarded the medal "Independence" on the occasion of the 1st anniversary of our country's independence. Along with educating young people, he has been a worthy example to young people by taking part in all competitions held among veterans, improving their sports skills. For example, in 2004, he won a bronze medal at the 2004 World Sambo Masters Championship held in Tajikistan, taking a proud 3rd place, and in 2007, he won a silver medal at the 2nd place in the World Uzbek Wrestling Masters Championship, held in Termiz. Since 2005, Mavlonberdi Akhmanov has been training young people in wrestling at the Karshi Olympic Reserve College. Most of his students are taking part in republican, international tournaments, and Asian championships and have been taking worthy places. [2-2]

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Athletes like Alisher Mukhtorov, the international master of sports in judo wrestling, a participant of the Olympic Games, also made the name of our region known to the world. He participated in the 1996 Atlanta Olympic Games and the 2000 Sydney Olympic Games. In addition, he became the champion of the republic several times, the winner and prize-winner of prestigious international tournaments.

Sofiya Kaspolatova, the honored athlete of the Republic of Uzbekistan, five-time Asian karate champion, was born on January 4, 1983. The permanent coach of the champion girl is Alisher Sodikov. Sofiya Kaspolatova became the Asian champion in karate-do (individual wrestling) in 1999 and won the silver medal in the World Championship in 2003. In June 2005, the national team of our country successfully participated in the next Asian karate championship held in Macau. Our compatriots won seven medals in competitions with hundreds of athletes from 37 countries. Sofia Kaspolatova, a student of Karshi State University, successfully participated in the team, and at first in her own weight, and then in absolute weight, there was no athlete who could match her on the continent. Even representatives of Japan, considered the homeland of karate, recognized Sofia's skills. According to foreign experts, Sofia's method of performing karate can be used as a lesson for others. Therefore, his exercises were recorded on video tapes by experts. [3-6]. Sofia, who has been working as a coach, was recognized as the best female coach of 2020.

Tursunoy Jabborova was born on March 4, 2002 in Kashkadarya region. He achieved his first success in weightlifting at the 2017 Asian Junior Championship. At that time, our athlete became the owner of a silver medal. After that, Tursunoy became the champion of Asia among teenagers and young people, the winner of world championships in these categories. He was awarded a silver medal at the 2019 World Cup. In 2021, he won the gold medal in the 87 kg weight class held in Konya, Turkey. He won a bronze medal at the 2022 Asian Weightlifting Championships in Manama, Bahrain. Tursunoy Jabborova became the absolute world champion in weight up to 87 kilograms at the weightlifting world championship held in Heraklion, Greece in May 2023. Our athlete lifted a 109 kg stone in the deadlift and 129 kg in the deadlift and won the gold medal in both events. Also, Jabborova was unequal according to the results of two fights.

At the 15th Paralympic Games held in Rio de Janeiro in 2016, student of Karshi State University Fatimakhon Amilova won a gold medal in swimming, and Shohsanamkhan Toshpolatova won 3 bronze medals. In addition, Shohsanamkhan Toshpolatova won the 1st place in the winter open championship of Uzbekistan dedicated to the memory of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov. In September 2019, the next world para-swimming championship was held in London, the capital of Great Britain, and Shohsanam Toshpolatova was the first to reach the finish line in the women's 100-meter butterfly and won the first gold medal in this world championship at the expense of the national team. Shohsanam Toshpolatova, who set a new Asian record with the result of 1 minute, 3.89 seconds, won the right to participate in the Paralympic Games "Tokyo-2020". [4-4].

In conclusion, we can say that in the years of independence, a number of activities were developed to popularize physical education and sports among all layers of the population. On the basis of these activities, the experience of establishing a healthy lifestyle among the population was accumulated, and the development of physical education and sports was raised to the level of state policy. As a result, the material and technical support of the industry in the republic was significantly strengthened. In such conditions, many sports facilities were built in Kashkadarya. Athletes and coaches from Kashkadarya are raising the country's flag high in the world arenas.

REFERENCES:

1. Акбар Раҳмон. "Насаф олға." // Қашқадарё ёшлар спорти, 2005-йил 13-май.
2. Қашқадарё вилояти давлат архиви, 591-фонд, 1-рўйхат, 1-варақ.
3. Алиқулов А. София Японияни лол қолдирди // Қашқадарё ёшлар спорти, 2005-йил 17-июнь.
4. Қарши университети, 2019-йил, сентябрь.

